

A photograph of a laboratory setting. In the foreground, a pipette with a pink handle and a clear tip is positioned over a petri dish containing a red agar medium. The petri dish is part of a multi-well tray. Other petri dishes are visible in the background, some containing blue and yellow media. The background is a soft, out-of-focus light blue.

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European Research Infrastructure
on Highly Pathogenic Agents

ERINHA

INTEGRATED CODE OF CONDUCT

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HISTORY OF CHANGES			
V #	Date	Description / Reason of change	Author
01	16 Feb 2026	Finalisation of first version	Jonathan EWBANK
02	25 Mar 2026	Incorporation of feedback from ERINHA Executive Board and Dr Åsa Björndal	Jonathan EWBANK
03	17 Apr 2026	Incorporation of feedback from ERINHA Members	Jonathan EWBANK
	13 May 2026	Endorsement by ERINHA General Assembly	

PREAMBLE

Advances in biological sciences have benefitted humanity immensely. They can, however, pose unintended risks, including through deliberate misuse, with the development of biological weapons being perhaps the most egregious. This Code of Conductⁱ seeks to foster a culture of responsibility, prudent biorisk management, and ethical awareness among the scientists and institutions that are part of the European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA AISBL), its staff, and the scientists that access its services. Individuals who participate in ERINHA actions in virtue of their affiliation to an entity that is an ERINHA AISBL Member would be expected to adhere to it. A commitment to adhere to it will condition the acceptance of requests for ERINHA services, or participation in ERINHA-coordinated projects, by others. For the avoidance of doubt, if these others are in countries that are not signatories to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Development, Production and Stockpiling of Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Weapons and on Their Destruction, they would be required to guarantee their permanent adherence to its provisions, in their personal capacity or at an institutional level, as appropriate.

1. ETHICAL STANDARDS

ERINHA AISBL staff will, through their actions, align with the following ethical standards:

- Respect human life, dignity, and rights.
- Uphold social ethics, cultural traditions, and moral standards.
- Maintain harmony between humanity and the ecological environment.
- Use biosciences only for peaceful and beneficial purposes.
- Guard against any misuse of science for malicious or harmful ends, including harm to the environment.

ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates, to adhere to them too.

2. LEGAL COMPLIANCE AND NORM AWARENESS

ERINHA AISBL staff will:

- Be aware of and comply with relevant national laws, international legal instruments, and ethical norms, including those prohibiting biological weapons, and those applying to the use of animals, particularly the need to reduce, refine and replace.
- When within their competence, contribute to the development and strengthening of legal frameworks and norms related to biosafety, biosecurity and responsible science.

ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates, similarly, to be aware, comply and contribute in these areas.

3. INTEGRITY AND RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH CONDUCT

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff, and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Uphold integrity and rigour in all activities.
- Avoid and actively prevent conflicts of interest.
- Avoid and actively prevent research misconduct.
- Acknowledge the dual-use nature of biological sciences and assess risks of potential misuse of biological research, products, knowledge, or equipment.

4. RESPECT IN RESEARCH

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Protect the welfare, rights, and privacy of human research participants, in accordance with all appropriate legal frameworks and norms.
- Apply the highest ethical standards in research conduct and ensure informed consent is obtained whenever required.
- Treat material of human origin with the respect it deserves.

5. RESEARCH PROCESS OVERSIGHT AND RISK MANAGEMENT

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Prevent misuse of equipment, knowledge, or facilities.
- Identify, assess, and manage potential risks at all stages of research and across all departments.
- Implement whole-process oversight mechanisms, including feasibility studies, threat analyses, risk prevention plans, and the responses to incidents and accidents.
- Ensure operational rules and review processes are in place to mitigate vulnerabilities.
- Establish independent risk review bodies and ethics committees if these are not already part of mandatory national requirements.
- Support transparency, compliance, and training throughout their operations.

6. DISSEMINATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

When applicable, to the extent permitted by laws and regulations, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Recognise their role in balancing scientific openness with public safety and biosecurity concerns.
- Communicate findings accurately to prevent misinterpretation or harmful misuse.
- Avoid disseminating sensitive data that could be exploited by those with malintent.
- Publicly condemn academic misconduct and promote ethical publishing standards.

7. EDUCATION AND TRAINING

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Develop comprehensive education and training systems that include legal, ethical, biosafety and biosecurity topics.
- Provide regular training involving experts from natural, social, and human sciences and thereby provide a more balanced perspective.
- Ensure all staff understand the broader implications of their work and act responsibly.

8. PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Communicate openly with the public about the importance of biological research as it underpins both human and animal well-being, but also risks of biological research.
- Identify target audiences and use appropriate communication tools to promote factual, balanced understanding.
- Work to dispel misinformation and reduce fear stemming from misunderstanding or disinformation.
- Encourage responsible reporting and oppose sensationalism in biotechnology coverage.
- Involve the public as much as possible in discussions addressing oversight of biological research.

9. INTERDISCIPLINARY DIALOGUE

When applicable, ERINHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to:

- Engage in collaboration with philosophers, anthropologists, ethicists, and social scientists to understand the societal and ethical dimensions of their work, anticipate potential impacts, address public concerns, and ensure that their research is conducted responsibly.

10. INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

When applicable, ERINHHA AISBL expects its Members, and requires its staff and third parties that are beneficiaries of its services or involved in projects it coordinates to::

- Promote peaceful innovation and responsible collaboration in biosciences across borders.
- Share best practices, knowledge, and expertise to improve global biosafety and biosecurity practises.
- Support mutual learning and assist in responding to biosafety and biosecurity threats.

ⁱ It reflects decades-long discussions about the responsibility that is carried by life scientists, particularly the obligation to “do no harm” (see for example the 2006 call for [A Hippocratic Oath for life scientists](#)). It is consistent with the norms of the Convention on the Prohibition of the Development, Production and Stockpiling of Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Weapons and on Their Destruction (aka the Biological Weapons Convention; [BWC](#)), the United Nations [Sustainable Development Goals](#), the ‘2005 InterAcademy Panel [statement on Biosecurity](#), and the World Medical Association’s [Declaration of Helsinki](#). It includes elements proposed for a BWC code of conduct from the [2005](#) and [2018](#) meetings of the States Parties to the BWC, as well as elements from the [Tianjin Biosecurity Guidelines for Codes of Conduct](#) and the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) developed by the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities. It should be read in conjunction with the relevant [regulatory frameworks](#), elements of the European Commission’s [guidelines for Responsible Research & Innovation](#), pertinent publications from the World Health Organization, including the “[Laboratory biosafety manual, 4th edition](#)”, its accompanying practical [implementation guide](#), “[Laboratory biosecurity guidance](#)” and “[Global guidance framework for the responsible use of the life sciences: mitigating biorisks and governing dual-use research](#)”, as well as the WHA77.7 Agenda item 14.1, “[Strengthening laboratory biological risk management](#)”, the [2025 Pandemic Agreement](#), the “Ten Key Components of U.S. Biosafety and Biosecurity” from the GAO’s 2026 comparative report [GAO-26-107338](#), the [ASEAN Leaders’ Declaration On Strengthening Regional Biosafety, And Biosecurity](#), and [CEPI’s Biosecurity Policy](#). ERINHHA gratefully recognises the contribution of Dr James Reville to the elaboration of this code of conduct.